

**SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF TEACHING PRIMARY CLASS
STUDENTS TO CREATIVE THINKING IN MOTHER LANGUAGE
LESSONS**

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Abstract: This article describes the problem of the use of interactive methods in primary education mother-tongue classes and the extent to which the effectiveness of the lesson increases. Also, the author commented on the features of using non-traditional methods to focus the student's attention, develop resourcefulness and creativity.

Key words: pedagogical technology, interactive method, ability, style, ingenuity, creativity, non-traditional methods.

"We will mobilize all the strength and capabilities of our state and society so that our young people can be independent thinkers, have high intellectual and spiritual potential, become people who will never leave their peers on the world scale, and become happy".

Sh.M.Mirziyoyev

It is known that the main task of primary education is to provide in-depth knowledge to students using methods that teach independent thinking and develop creative thinking. To fulfill this task, new pedagogical technologies were introduced into the educational process. New pedagogical technologies play an important role in the mental development and maturation of primary school students. One of the most popular types of pedagogical technologies today is interactive methods. Interactive methods are a joint activity of the student and the teacher and teach students to think creatively, come to the necessary conclusions, analyze and apply the acquired knowledge in practice. The main task of the teacher is to give clear direction to the students and to tell the correct conclusions. Interactive methods are also important because the teacher never sharply rejects the student's opinion, but only gives the correct conclusion, as a result, the student realizes his mistake and does not stop thinking, and there is constant activity between them. is provided.

In world pedagogical practice, the development of educational motivation is recognized as a factor of increasing students' interest in learning, mastering the basics of science, and stimulating independent cognitive activities. It is especially important to develop students' creative thinking based on the innovative

didactic system of developing students' creative thinking, the competence approach based on Life Skills.

While we are talking about "Creativity" in this article, let's first get acquainted with the introduction of this term into science. The word creativity was first used in 1922 by the American scientist D. Simpson. This term describes the ability of a person to abandon a mold, a stereotype, a habitual way of thinking.

Creativity is a person's ability to come up with an unusual idea, idea, to find a non-repetitive, original solution to problems, to abandon traditional forms of thinking. Rodgers (1944) understands creativity as a new solution to problems and new ways of expressing something, an event, a situation.

Creativity is the creative ability of an individual that describes the readiness to produce new ideas and is part of talent as an independent factor. A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings, and certain types of activities.

It is known that the attention of young children is unstable, which causes some problems for the 1st grader. In this situation, interesting interactive methods are of great importance in concentrating students' attention. Completing pictorial assignments to students encourages them to think, ingenuity, and creativity, and increases their vocabulary by developing their written and oral speech. The following methods give effective results in developing the ingenuity of primary school students, the ability to remember letters: "Sunflower" method. In the middle of the picture of a sunflower, there are ova uunli, and consonant letters are written around it. Students make several words by adding consonants and single vowel letters. It is also possible to change middle vowels during the game. Pupils independently write their words in their notebooks. All students participate equally in this process.

The teacher encourages and evaluates the most active participants during the training. We can use this method in both writing lessons and alphabet lessons. The more letters a student learns, the more letters he can add to make words. We can make such words from the letters given in the first and second sunflower. For example: world, cherry, father, sky, master, brother, sleep. After completing the alphabet textbook, the 1st grade mother tongue book first gives students information about "Sound and Letter". The topics gradually become more complex. This situation creates a certain difficulty and causes the students to get bored of the lesson. In such cases, the use of interactive methods gives effective results. Our sunflower method shown above is a clear example of this. The initial exercises of the "Sound and letter" section are also given to form

students' oral speech. The lesson can be strengthened through this method. This method helps to make mother tongue lessons interesting, prevent students from getting bored in the lessons, and evaluate more students in a shorter period of time. "Sinquain" method. Cinquain means "five" and means "an unrhymed five-line poem." Students write a five-line poem that doesn't rhyme using the Cinquain method. Accordingly, the first line should consist of one word and it should be a word belonging to the noun group, the second line should consist of two words and it should be a word belonging to the adjective group to be, the third line should consist of three words, and this verb should be words related to the word group, the fourth line should be a complete proverb, and the fifth line should be a synonym of the word in the first line a word can be put. This method can be used after the students have an understanding of word groups after entering the 2nd and 3rd grades. In the 2nd grade native language textbook, in the vocabulary section, the first morphological concepts are given about the words that express the name, action, sign, count and order of a person and thing.

The teacher listens to the student's opinion and, at the same time, teaches the students to pay attention to each other's words. Objections or additions are expressed by words such as "respected", "agree with your opinion", "we also had some opinions". In the lesson organized in this way, the student begins to think freely without any pressure and openly expresses his thoughts, and learns to respect others. In primary education, the mother tongue students' logical thinking, increasing vocabulary, developing oral and written speech (that is, reading and writing correctly), phonetics, lexis, vocabulary z should be made and serve to create a foundation for learning grammar. It is known that conducting vocabulary work in the class of the mother tongue makes students curious about the meaning of words that are unfamiliar to them. It is advisable for the student to independently search for the explanation of these words. In this case, the following method not only increases students' vocabulary, but also teaches them how to work with a dictionary. The use of interactive methods in lessons should be organized in such a way that all students in the class should be active, that is, during the course of the lesson, a certain part of the educational materials will be studied by students independently. The teacher is the organizer, leader, and supervisor of the educational process. Pupils should feel free in the classroom and educational activities should satisfy him emotionally, only then he can express his thoughts freely.

Among the many factors that determine the development of creative abilities of a primary school student, creative thinking, imagination, thinking, and communication skills can be developed in the process of mastering exercises in mother tongue classes. In this process, the child and the teacher together become a system of open problems subject to the child's clear creative thinking. This process should be done in a way that is convenient for the young student. Within this theory, the effective use of methods that develop creative thinking ensures the success of the lesson, which is determined by the creation of a pedagogical script by the teacher and the mastery of the indicative basis of new actions by young students in the process of creative activity. The following are the methods of conducting and organizing native language lessons in primary grades, developing creative thinking:

Intrusion method. It consists in simultaneously perceiving different types of exercises. This method contributes to the creation of a complete artistic text, more complete assimilation of information, due to deep penetration into the world of sound and words, it evokes a lively emotional and emotional response.

Contradiction method. It is carried out in the form of a contrast of tasks in various exercises. The confrontation method allows to contrast tasks, arouse interest in students, activates the manifestation of emotional response. For each lesson, the teacher should choose such a range that will help young students to develop interest in the world around them.

In short, the teacher should know this technology thoroughly and be able to use it correctly based on the characteristics of the language materials studied in practice. The more effective forms of teaching are used, the higher the level of interest of students in the subject of their mother tongue.

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